

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

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Sample

Sample name: ARN039 [Cu(POP)(1,1'-biisoquinoline)][PF ₆]	
Aspect / texture: Powder	
Molecular formula: C ₅₄ H ₄₀ CuF ₆ N ₂ OP ₃	Molar mass: 1003.38
Used solvent: Dichloromethane, Diethylether	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name: ARN039

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements: Cu, P, O, F		

Results

Analysis number: 2020-54			
Sample name: ARN039			
Expected values:	C 64.64 %	H 4.02 %	N 2.79 %
Results:	C 64.38 % - %	H 4.00 % - %	N 2.94 % - %
Other elements:			
Remarks: When F → single determination → HF			

Date/Visa operator
 29.07.2020, Sylvie Mittelheisser